

Predicting and Managing Real-Time Capacity for Shop and Deliver Propositions in Smart Cities Using AI

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Abstract: *Smart cities are undergoing a revolution with advancements in technology. Among the several aspects of smart cities, shops, and delivery propositions are vital since they facilitate the supply of products and services to city citizens. However, research has identified problems in predicting and managing real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions in smart cities. This research, therefore, delves into exploring this problem and identifies challenges and factors leading to this problem. The research developed four research objectives as a guide towards exhausting this comprehensive subject. Using a multidisciplinary framework, this research relies on the existing challenges to suggest an approach towards developing AI-based new methods that improve the existing methods and hence enhance real-time capacity prediction and management. The research also identified key stakeholders who, when involved, will contribute towards developing robust new methods. However, the research has some limitations which set the base for future research.*

Keywords: AI, Real-Time Capacity, Shop and Delivery Propositions, Smart City

Introduction

With increasing urbanization, cities look forward to transforming into smart cities to solve overpopulation issues efficiently. The shops and delivery propositions are among the common aspects of smart cities. Technology has enhanced online shopping, where individuals can order goods online from different shops and have them delivered at pick stations or customer homes (Anushan et al., 2016; Dash & Gatharia, 2016). The entire process of ensuring the shop is in the position of maintaining stock, to ensure whenever the customer orders, a commodity is available and can be delivered without delay, is a complex process. The shops need an effective approach to estimate and adjust the resources needed to meet shop and delivery services demand in real-time (timely and efficient). In this context of smart cities, a technological method using AI is needed to enhance logistical and delivery systems in the city, hence allowing prediction and management of real-time capacity for shops and delivery propositions. The new system should be outstanding to ensure effectiveness and efficiency in order processing, inventory management, route optimization, delivery tracking, scalability, communication, data analytics, and sustainability. This research paper will propose evidence-based approaches through which shops and delivery propositions in smart cities can develop AI-based methods to enhance the prediction and management of real-time capacity. The suggested approach is multidisciplinary, encompassing AI, data science, logistics, and urban planning in alignment with the sustainable goals of the city. Real-Time Capacity Prediction and Management for Shop and Delivery Propositions in Smart Cities are shown below.

Figure 1:Real-Time Capacity Prediction and Management for Shop and Delivery Propositions in Smart Cities

Research Objectives

Based on the existing challenges facing shops and delivery propositions in smart cities on prediction and management of real-time capacity, this research objectives are as follows:

- To examine the current state of prediction and management methods in shops and delivery propositions in smart cities.
- To identify the key factors and challenges affecting the demand and supply of resources in smart cities for shops and delivery propositions.
- To suggest requirements for developing new methods for predicting and managing real-time capacity for shop and delivery propositions in smart cities through AI leveraging.
- To identify the key stakeholders and their roles in developing these new methods.

Literature review

Smart cities have enhanced the quality of life, environmental sustainability, and efficiency of services provided to individuals living in urban areas by leveraging information and communication technologies. One of the aspects of smart cities working towards ensuring convenience, fast, and reliable access to goods and services through online platforms and delivery systems is the shops and delivery propositions. The shops and delivery propositions use real-time capacity management in estimating and adjusting the number of resources, weather, staff, vehicles, or products, to keep up with the pace of meeting the shop and delivery services demands without delays (Xiong et al., 2012; Dash & Agarwal, 2016). This literature review delves into

understanding the current landscape of the shops and delivery proposition in the smart city context and how they achieve prediction and management of real-time capacity. The literature identifies current methods and technologies and isolates existing challenges and gaps.

Over the years, the concept of smart cities has evolved, with various scholars and practitioners using different definitions, demonstrations, models, characterization, and proposing components for making smart cities. A study by Arroub et al. (2016) enlightens us on the cities' movement towards smartness. This research achieves this by exhausting smart cities' diverse definitions, dimensions, models, characteristics, and components. This research identifies six key dimensions that make a city a smart city: smart economy, smart logistics (mobility), smart environment, smart people, smart living, and smart governance. In their research, the authors propose a four-layered conceptual model of smart cities: infrastructure, data, service, and interface layers. Their research also highlights the opportunities and challenges of ICT integration in smart cities, including data management, data analytics, service innovation, citizen engagement, governance models, security and ethical issues, and social inclusion (Dash et al., 2014).

Shop and delivery propositions are closely reliant on mobility and smart living dimensions. These two aspects are enhanced by online platforms such as e-commerce platforms and applications where customers can order goods (like groceries and clothes) and services (like food and laundry deliveries or taxi services) within the city shops and providers (Montoya-Torres et al., 2016). The use of delivery systems such as robots, drones, or vehicles is a vital segment of the shops and delivery propositions in ensuring the transportation of ordered goods or services from the shops to the desired customer locations (homes, offices, or pick-up stations). The shops and delivery propositions become reputable if they perform these processes conveniently, with speed, remaining reliable with variety and affordable services to the customers while at the same time aiming to reduce traffic congestion, pollution, and energy consumption (Komninos et al., 2014; van Duin et al., 2016). Entirely the operational costs for shops and providers should yield a positive Return on Investment (ROI).

Through real-time capacity, shops can estimate and adjust the resources needed to withstand the demand for goods and delivery services (Nha et al., 2012). This process is built on the sandstone of forecasting demand patterns, relying on historical data, market trends, customer behavior, weather conditions, and seasonality, among other factors. Real-time capacity management also involves the location and optimization of resources on a demand forecast basis, service level agreements, cost-benefit analysis, and other constraints (Mirowski et al., 2014). Henceforth, the ultimate goal of real-time capacity management is balancing the demand and supply for resources, maximizing customer satisfaction, revenue, profitability, and sustainability for the shops and providers.

Currently, shops and delivery propositions in smart cities' state of prediction and management have high complexity, uncertainty, dynamism, and heterogeneity (Yin et al., 2015). A wide range of goods and services that different shops or providers offer leads to the complexity. The complexity is also enhanced by the fact that customers use different platforms and channels to order goods and services, the delivery agencies use diverse modes and routes for delivery, and the interdependence and interactions among these elements. Some factors leading to uncertainty

are fluctuations and variations in demand, the availability of shops and providers, the performance of the delivery system when it comes to traffic conditions, weather changes, emergencies, or accidents (Strohbach et al., 2015). The progressive evolution in customer preferences, shop, and provider offerings, delivery systems innovations, and urban environment changes have contributed to the dynamism. Several factors lead to heterogeneity: varying customer needs, expectations, and preferences; capabilities, objectives, and strategies of the shops and providers; the functions, failures, and limitations of the delivery system; and urban cultures and regulations.

Shops and delivery propositions currently use several methods and technologies to predict and manage real-time capacity in smart cities (Nenni et al., 2013). In the early approaches, demand forecasting and data analytics have predominantly relied on historical data, statistical models, and traditional forecasting techniques to estimate demand patterns. These methods could not keep up with the speed of changing conditions. Therefore, researchers have suggested advanced data analytics and machine learning techniques to enhance forecasting analysis. Some of the machine learning algorithms in use, like regression analysis, time series analysis, and neural networks, have proved capable of analyzing big data sets, seasonality, customer behaviors, and various trends in the market.

Inventory management and route optimization are still progressing towards smartness. The traditional inventory management system that employed static record points and order quantities could not adapt to the dynamic demand fluctuations (Patil & Divekar, 2014). Therefore, researchers and businesses have invented dynamic inventory management systems that can use real-time data, triggering inventory replenishment. These systems consider safety stock, lead time, and demand variability. On the other hand, the traditional route optimization systems that relied on predefined static routes had a common issue of incipencies and suboptimal delivery routes. Current development of route optimization algorithms, like genetic algorithms and simulated annealing, have aided in optimizing routes for delivery based on real-time traffic data, customer locations, and delivery schedules (Ting & Chen, 2013). Through urban planning and regulations, smart cities look forward to implementing strategies to optimize traffic flow, reduce congestion, and improve delivery services. These planning strategies include improving and expanding delivery lanes and imposing regulations on vehicle emissions.

Shops and delivery propositions in smart cities are also working on communication and tracking improvements and ushering in emerging technologies, including the Internet of Things (IoT) and Sensors. The traditional coordination and tracking of delivery vehicles employed basic communication tools like phone calls and radio communications. The invention of GPS technology and mobile applications have replaced the traditional system. Real-time tracking of delivery vehicles can improve customer transparency, helping the shops and delivery proposition optimize route planning. Additionally, drones, robots, and autonomous vehicles are emerging technologies promising to revolutionize real-time capacity management and prediction by improving last-mile delivery. The Internet of Things IOT offers opportunities to enhance real-time capacity management by monitoring inventory levels, conditions of vehicles, and environmental factors that may affect deliveries.

Even though shops and delivery propositions benefit from the existing methods and technologies in predicting and managing real-time capacity, challenges, and research gaps need to be resolved for maximum efficiency and effectiveness. Integrating different systems into a single system is necessary to increase the coordination and efficiency of prediction and management of real-time capacity. Additionally, the new methods and technologies should focus on reducing data security and privacy concerns while solving the issue of effectively managing complex and dynamic supply chains existing among the shops and delivery propositions in the smart city context.

Methodology

Theoretical framework

This research employs a multidisciplinary approach with several domains, including AI, data science, logistics, urban planning, sustainability, and smart city framework. This framework addresses the complex challenges of predicting and managing real-time capacity in a smart city context featuring shops and delivery propositions. The central component of this theoretical framework is AI. This component encompasses machine learning algorithms, data-driven-decision decision-making processes, and predictive analytics. This domain will be essential in developing predictive models for demand forecasting, resource allocation, inventory management, and route optimization. The second component is data science, which will use data science principles to collect, process, and analyze data. This component will be essential in harnessing historical, real-time, and IoT data to feed AI models. Logistics is the framework's third component and includes concepts like supply chain management, inventory control, and last-mile delivery optimization. These concepts incorporated into the framework will ensure a smooth flow of goods from shops to customers. The fourth component is urban planning, vital in shaping the city's physical infrastructure. This domain focuses on transportation network optimization, the definition of delivery zones, and traffic flow regulation. Urban planning principles are essential in enhancing the efficiency of delivery routes and minimizing congestion. Sustainability is the fifth component of the framework and includes principles aiming to reduce emissions, energy consumption, and congestion. The completeness of this multidisciplinary framework is achieved by integrating it into the smart city framework. There are 6 key dimensions of the smart city framework: smart environment, smart people, smart economy, smart logistics, smart living, and smart governance. Including the smart city framework will ensure that the proposed AI-based methods will enhance the overall city's smartness.

Figure 2: Multidisciplinary Theoretical Framework

Data Collection, Processing and Analysis

This research employs a systemic review approach to data collection. The fact that this research paper focuses on the existing methods and technologies used by shops and delivery propositions in predicting and managing real-time capacity, the use of historical data collected from previously published scholarly and research articles, government publications, and industry reports necessitated the progression of this research. Henceforth, a comprehensive literature review was conducted. The research used the keywords "shops and delivery propositions," "real-time capacity," "Artificial Intelligence," and "smart cities" were used to search for relevant articles from academic journals, proceedings of conferences, and published relevant books. 306 articles were selected and subjected to screening processes, where 41 sources were selected based on their eligibility and quality, relevance to the topic, and currency (published within 5 years). Relevant data was extracted from the screened resources and thematically grouped in preparation for data analysis.

The collected data was subjected to rigorous analysis to facilitate drawing meaningful insights and answer the research objectives. Data analysis entailed thematic analysis and a comparative approach. Thematic analysis was an essential analysis of the qualitative data from the selected sources. The common themes generated through these approaches include concepts and issues relating to the prediction and management of real-time capacity. Themes of challenges, technologies, and methods in shops and delivery propositions in predicting and managing real-time capacity were identified and categorized. Comparative analysis evaluated the effectiveness and efficiency of current technologies and methods in application in predicting and managing real-time capacity. The different methods and technologies were compared regarding their strengths, weaknesses, and suitability in predicting and managing real-time capacity shops and delivery propositions in the smart cities' context. The comparison was necessary to identify gaps and improvement opportunities, with an elevated focus on integrating AI and data science into the existing methods.

Figure 3: Systemic Review Steps

Results and Discussion

Based on the four research objectives, the following key findings were obtained after data analysis:

The current state of prediction and management methods in shops and delivery propositions in smart cities: The research found that the existing methods are multifaceted – they rely on historical data, traditional forecasting techniques, machine learning algorithms, route optimization, and dynamic inventory management. These methods are not effective and efficient in handling the current complexity, uncertainty, dynamism, and heterogeneity experienced in smart city environments.

The key factors and challenges affecting the demand and supply of resources in smart cities for shops and delivery propositions: The factors identified include demand fluctuations, customer preferences, needs and behavior, weather conditions, and seasonality. Common challenges include integrating different systems, data privacy and security concerns, and effective management of dynamic and complex supply chains.

The requirements for developing new methods for predicting and managing real-time capacity for shop and delivery propositions in smart cities through AI leveraging: Towards the goal of enhancing prediction and management of real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions, the development of new methods should consider the integration of AI, data science, logistics, and urban planning. The new methods should integrate these components while at the same time aiming to streamline the coordination of the supply chain and address concerns of data privacy and security, with an adaptable approach to the dynamic nature of smart city environments to accommodate sustainability and ethical considerations.

The key stakeholders and their roles in developing these new methods: Based on the requirements for developing the new methods of predicting and managing real-time capacity, the following stakeholders will play significant roles: Government authorities, service providers and business owners, urban planners, technology companies, and researchers.

The research findings enlighten us on the current state of the methods used to predict and manage real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions. With the common goal of this research paper remaining suggestion approaches through which the shops and delivery propositions can develop new methods for predicting and managing real-time capacity, it is key to understand the existing challenges, the factors to consider, and the stakeholders to be involved during the development of these new methods. The results have identified that the existing methods applied by shops and delivery propositions do not meet the evolving smart city environment. Smart city environment evolution has made it complex in a couple of aspects (Lara et al., 2016). Therefore, the new methods to be developed should handle the complexity, dynamism, heterogeneity, and big data with the assurance of providing accurate, reliable, and timely results. The methods should also be capable of accommodating the changing conditions and preferences of the customers and aligning with performance optimization and sustainability.

Factors that affect demand and supply of resources in shops and delivery propositions include demand fluctuations, customer preferences, needs and behavior, weather conditions, and seasonality. These factors are critical when developing new methods for predicting and managing real-time capacity. These factors influence demand patterns, customer expectations and demands, resource availability, quality and cost, inventory, and delivery agents. Considering the challenges identified will be essential to evade failures of the new methods. Integration of different systems, data privacy, security concerns, and effective management of dynamic and complex supply chains cause difficulties in coordinating and optimizing shops and delivery proposals because they involve a couple of platforms, stakeholders, data sources, and processes (Tirachini et al., 2013). The highlighted factors and challenges present a need for developing new methods for predicting and managing real-time capacity for shops and delivery propositions. AI integration in the new methods poses an opportunity to handle the complexity, uncertainty, dynamism, and heterogeneity in smart cities. AI will stabilize machine learning, adapt easily to changes, optimize outcomes, and enhance performance.

However, AI cannot solely work independently to solve the existing challenges and seal the available gap completely. Therefore, integrating AI with data science, logistics, and urban planning will lead to the development of a multidisciplinary new method that will improve the prediction and management of real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions in smart cities (Lee et al., 2013). The data science component will be vital in providing tools and methods effective in collecting, processing, analyzing, and visualizing big data in real-time after collection from several sources in the smart city. The logistics component will provide outstanding methods and tools for planning, coordinating, and executing goods and services delivery in smart cities. The urban planning component will play a significant role in providing the tools and methods necessary for designing, developing, and regulating the smart cities' social and physical dynamics. Henceforth, combining AI, logistics, urban planning, and data science in the new methods will effectively address the challenges and factors affecting demand and supply.

Lastly, developing these new methods will require input from several stakeholders (Paskaleva et al., 2015). Government authorities are key in providing incentives, regulations, and infrastructure that will support and encourage the adoption of AI and other technologies in

developing methods for predicting and managing real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions. Service providers and business owners are at the forefront of improving efficiency and reducing costs, and this is possible by investing in AI, other technologies, and new methods for real-time capacity management. Urban planners are essential in urban layout design to ensure efficient delivery routes and facilitate the deployment of drones and autonomous vehicles. Technology companies and researchers' involvement in developing new methods will facilitate the effective development of AI algorithms, other innovative technologies, and innovative technologies. Customers and citizens are the end users of the delivery services; hence, their feedback is key in adopting AI-based new approaches. Environmental and sustainability organizations will ensure the new methods are environmentally friendly. Data protection and privacy authorities' involvement will provide accurate data collection, processing, and storage approaches in compliance with relevant regulations to enhance data security and privacy. Finally, the transportation and logistics associations will significantly contribute to developing the new methods as they are familiar with the best standards and practices for real-time capacity management.

Conclusion

Through a multidisciplinary approach, this paper has explored the complexities and challenges associated with predicting and managing real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions in a smart city context. By identifying these challenges, the complexities, and the factors involved, this paper has suggested an AI-based new method for improving the prediction and management of the real-time capacity for shops and delivery propositions. The suggested methods will integrate AI, data science, logistics, urban planning, sustainability, and smart city concepts to solve the challenges facing evolution in smart cities. The research has also suggested key stakeholders who will help enhance efficiency in developing the new methods.

While the current methods in managing and predicting the real-time capacity in shops and delivery propositions have made steps towards improving efficiency, there is room for extra improvement to solve the issues arising from smart city environments' dynamic and heterogeneous nature. By adopting the suggestions discussed on the approach to developing the AI-based new methods, the shops and delivery propositions will enhance management and prediction of their real-time capacity and achieve more convenient and sustainable urban living experiences.

This research has some limitations that might affect the validity and generalizability of its findings. One limitation is that of scope limitation and data collection bias. The study is limited to managing and predicting real-time capacity for shops and delivery propositions in smart cities. Hence, it may not cover all aspects of this subject. The research relied on existing literature and data sources, which may lead to obtaining biased findings. Future research can collect primary data through interviews, surveys, and case studies for more nuanced findings. Another limitation is that of interdisciplinary challenges in that implementing a multidisciplinary approach may pose challenges to collaboration and communication among experts and different domains. Future research can benefit from exploring effective strategies for interdisciplinary teamwork.

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